

RDA Council Nominations Committee Terms of Reference

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Research Data Alliance (RDA) Council Nominations Committee

Terms of Reference

Version 0.2 Approved by Council 29 June 2022

Originally approved as Council Nominations Committee Selection Process and Guidelines by Council on 28 May 2016

Merged with Council Nominations Committee Terms of Reference, also originally approved by Council on 28 May 2016 in June 2022

1 Selection Process and Guidelines

1.1 Context

Council should be a senior body of statespersons not explicitly representing any constituency. They need to be mindful of the needs of funders, the membership, partners, and all relevant stakeholders, but also willing to make difficult strategic decisions that may not please all. While a fully democratic approach to selecting Council members is not appropriate because it would introduce partisan lobbying and special interests, it *is* appropriate for the Nominations Committee to represent diverse interests.

It is essential that Council have the trust and confidence of the funding agencies supporting RDA operations. It is equally essential that Council have the trust and confidence of the RDA membership. RDA must also be seen as a neutral, authoritative, and effective body by the broader research and data sharing community. Finally, prospective Council members must understand the work involved and a willingness to work in a collaborative, community-driven, consensus-based environment.

1.2 Composition & Characteristics

Members of the Committee should have an understanding of RDA and support its aims and objectives. They should be able to work together to build a slate that reflects the tasks and purposes of the RDA Council.

It is a requirement of being a member of the Nominations Committee that they do not nominate for election to the RDA Council for the period in question.

1.3 Terms

The considerations above inform the following process:

- Council appoints a new Nomination Committee every year at least six months before the

opening of the annual Council election vote.

- The Nomination Committee shall consist of four to seven individuals, with at least one representative from the following stakeholder constituencies:
 - Funding agencies currently supporting central RDA operations
 - The general individual membership chosen by Council
 - The organisational membership and affiliates chosen by Council from Organisational Assembly
 - Former or Departing Council members
- A new Nomination Committee is appointed every year, but there is no limit on how long someone can serve on the committee, and Council should ensure some continuity in membership from year to year.
- Council should ensure there is reasonably broad regional representation on the committee.
- Council should determine the members of the committee through a consensus-based approach.

2 Guidelines for the Nomination Committee

When developing the slate of Council candidates, the nominations committee should try to identify senior states people who do not represent any particular constituency or organization. In fact, Council members are required to serve in an individual capacity. Council members should have broad connections with funders, one or more research or data communities, and other relevant stakeholders.

Potential candidates should confirm that they are able to accept a fiduciary role and, where necessary, vote on decisions. Council members are registered as Directors of the Research Data Alliance Foundation¹ for the entire duration of their term(s).

The committee should also strive for a balanced representation on the Council in terms of:

Region:

- North America and South America
- Europe and Africa
- Asia and Oceania

Gender

In the spirit of the RDA Guiding Principles on inclusivity, gender balance on the RDA Council is essential and we strive for gender balance based on a goal 40:40:20 (40% men, 40% women and 20% open) – at all levels of our governance bodies. This commitment is grounded in a core belief: to attract, recruit, retain and

¹ A non-profit charitable organisation registered as a legal entity in the UK and is the official and legal representative of the RDA community as a whole. The RDA Foundation's legal headquarters are at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Harwell Oxford, Didcot, Oxfordshire, OX11 0QX, United Kingdom. RDA Foundation is a charitable company limited by guarantee. The company was incorporated under a Memorandum of Association on 1 May 2014 and is a registered charity, charity number 1162762. It received charitable status on 21 July 2015.

promote the best candidates, and to reap the diversity dividend, we must tap into the full talent pool. ²

Science & Technology (S&T) Discipline

RDA applies the Fields of Science and Technology FOST 2015³ in the OECD Frascati model to classify R&D into fields which are then divided into 42 second level fields.

1. Natural sciences
2. Engineering and technology
3. Medical and health sciences
4. Agricultural sciences
5. Social sciences
6. Humanities

3 RDA Nominations Committee Roles and Responsibilities

The RDA Council appoints the Nominations Committee, confirmed its membership and provides an overview of the election characteristics (which seats are open for election, what regions, which Council members are stepping down or standing for a second term, etc.)

The RDA Nominations Committee informs the Council of the outcome of their deliberations, delivering a confidential report summarising the discussions and decisions. In the event of non-agreement between Nomination Committee members, resignation of a member, or other irresolvable matters, the Nominations Committee chair, or one of its members if the chair is directly implicated, should contact Council Co-chairs and ask for their intervention.

4 The Task of the Nominations Committee

The task is to propose a set of candidates for election by the RDA global community that reflects the overall work of the RDA Council and its current balance. This set of candidates should be arrived at with a view towards reflecting the interests of the key stakeholders of RDA. In particular the candidates should be chosen to ensure the confidence of both the funders of RDA and the participants in RDA, in the RDA Council.

5 Process for the Nominations Committee

The overall process for the work of Nominations Committee is as follows:

Work done for the Nominations Committee:

² https://championsofchangecoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/MCC-40-40-40-Talent-Processes-Toolkit-2019_Web_Final.pdf

³ OECD (2015), Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>. For classification (see annex)

1. Council determines who will be standing down from Council, and who will re-stand
2. RDA Secretariat publishes the Call for Nominations

Work done by the Nominations Committee:

1. The Nominations Committee determines the Committee Chair
2. Potential Nominees submit their nominations
3. The Nominations Committee has an initial teleconference to consider thenominations and the current shape of the RDA Council
4. The Nominations Committee develops a proposed set of candidates for consideration
5. The Nominations Committee formally endorses a proposed set of candidates (email/teleconference as determined)
6. The Council is informed of the set of candidates and a confidential report with a summary of the decisions is made available, terminating the role of the Nominations Committee in this process.
7. The set of candidates is announced on a date determined by the Secretariat, in accordance with the Council co-chairs and the Nominations Committee Chair.
8. Voting opens and all RDA registered community members are eligible to vote for the set of candidates according to the Council Election procedures outlined in the RDA Governance Document.
9. Voting closes and the election outcome is announced by Secretariat
10. Elected candidates are informed of start date
11. Council members concluding their term step down.

6 Nominations Committee Guiding Principles

The Nominations Committee members agree to adhere to the RDA Guiding Principles and the RDA Code of Conduct.

The Nominations Committee members should be familiar with and adhere to the RDA conflict of interest policy and declare any potential conflict of interest at any time if it arises to the Secretary General.

Annex OECD FRASCATI classification

BROAD CLASSIFICATION	Second-level classification
1. NATURAL SCIENCES	1.1 Mathematics
	1.2 Computer and information sciences
	1.3 Physical sciences
	1.4 Chemical sciences
	1.5 Earth and related environmental sciences
	1.6 Biological sciences
	1.7 Other natural sciences
2. ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY	2.1 Civil engineering
	2.2 Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering
	2.3 Mechanical engineering
	2.4 Chemical engineering
	2.5 Materials engineering
	2.6 Medical engineering
	2.7 Environmental engineering
	2.8 Environmental biotechnology
	2.9 Industrial biotechnology
	2.10 Nanotechnology
	2.11 Other engineering and technologies
3. MEDICAL AND HEALTH SCIENCES	3.1 Basic medicine
	3.2 Clinical medicine
	3.3 Health sciences
	3.4 Medical biotechnology
	3.5 Other medical science
4. AGRICULTURAL AND VETERINARY SCIENCES	4.1 Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries
	4.2 Animal and dairy science
	4.3 Veterinary science
	4.4 Agricultural biotechnology
	4.5 Other agricultural sciences
5. SOCIAL SCIENCES	5.1 Psychology and cognitive sciences
	5.2 Economics and business
	5.3 Education
	5.4 Sociology
	5.5 Law
	5.6 Political science
	5.7 Social and economic geography
	5.8 Media and communications
	5.9 Other social sciences
6. HUMANITIES AND THE ARTS	6.1 History and archaeology
	6.2 Languages and literature
	6.3 Philosophy, ethics and religion
	6.4 Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
	6.5 Other humanities